

Schizophrenia as a disease of adaptation

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Abstract

Introduction: Currently, the etiology and pathogenesis of schizophrenia are unknown. Existing models of the disease do not reflect its internal essence, adaptive nature, and historical roots.

Purpose of the work: Present the author's view of the nature of schizophrenia as a process of forming a specific emotional-volitional defect, which is an adaptive form of functioning of the central nervous system, the brain, and the entire organism as a single whole, in conditions of frustration, blockage of the realization of an actual need.

Main provisions: According to the author, schizophrenia involves a transition of the central nervous system, the brain, and the entire organism as a whole to a lower basic adaptive energy-saving level of vital activity. Clinically, this manifests itself in the form of a specific emotional-volitional defect, the essence of which is an energy defect. At the same time, ancient defense mechanisms are released—schizophrenia, autism, apathy, abulia, and catatonia. The formation of an emotional-volitional defect leads to the removal of nervous and mental tension and frustration and the preservation of the structural and functional organization of the organism in pathological conditions. Schizophrenia is based on adaptive mechanisms of biological regression, the formation of pathological homeostasis, an increase in the threshold of basic reactivity and entropy. The clinical forms of schizophrenia reflect the body's innate adaptive response programs. According to the hypothesis, the positive symptoms of schizophrenia are nonspecific and reflect the general patterns of the body's response to stressors. The emotional-volitional defect in schizophrenia is primary, reflecting the adaptive nature and historical roots of schizophrenia. Cognitive disorders in the disease are secondary, projecting the emotional-volitional defect onto the cognitive functions of the central nervous system and brain in the form of anosognosia, a decrease in their motivational component, and goal setting. The level of progression of schizophrenia is determined by the depth of the emotional-volitional defect. Its clinical types reflect the scale of energy deficiency in the central nervous system, the brain, and the entire body as a whole.

Conclusion: Transition of the central nervous system, the brain, and the entire organism as a holistic system to a lower, stable, energy-saving level of functioning is a universal biological adaptation and reflects the internal nature and historical roots of schizophrenia. This leads to the formation of an emotional-volitional defect, which is an adaptive form of functioning of the biological system in pathological conditions; ancient defense mechanisms are released – schisis, autism, apathy, abulia, catatonia. The inner essence of the emotional-volitional defect is an energy defect.

This review presents a theoretical hypothesis on the adaptive nature of schizophrenia.

Keywords: biological system, schizophrenia, energy level, neuropsychiatric defect, adaptation.

Introduction

Currently, the etiology of schizophrenia is unknown [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. Existing models of the disease do not reflect its inner essence, adaptive nature, and historical roots [6].

Hereditary factors are known to play a role in the genesis of the disease; however, the genes responsible for schizophrenia are not eliminated through natural selection due to the adaptive nature of the disease [7].

The dopamine model of schizophrenia is simplified. Meanwhile, any clinical phenomenon reflects evolutionary processes and systemic adaptation, rather than being an arbitrary consequence of dysfunction or damage to biological structures [6].

E. Krepelin's theory of registers [1] speaks of the polyetiology of neuropsychiatric disorders, the clinical presentation of which, in his opinion, depends solely on the depth of damage to the nervous system.

The positive syndromes of the first rank described by K. Schneider [8], which are included in the ICD-10 criteria for schizophrenia, are nonspecific and reflect the general patterns of the body's response to harm [6, 9, DSM-5].

The adaptive-compensatory paradigm of schizophrenia is

Discussion

The organism is an open biological system capable of maintaining the constancy of its internal environment through homeostasis mechanisms [11]. Homeostasis is the moment of integrity and independence of the organism from the ecosystem, which dictates its morph functional structure through natural selection.

The organism, as a holistic biological system, is formed through the reflection of actual needs and the reciprocal initiation of self-regulation processes aimed at satisfying these needs, which leads to homeostasis and the preservation of the system. A violation of homeostasis is the essence of its destruction and death.

Reactivity is the main property of life. Reactivity is the ability of an organism to respond internally to the demands of the ecosystem, the form of its interaction with it, a special type of reflection associated with the regulation of homeostasis. The integrative factor of the organism's vital activity, as a holistic system, is the reflected need, and the system-forming reactive structure is the basal nuclei of the brain, the emotional centers.

The development of emotions originates from the reflexive loop and basal ganglia of homeostasis regulation,

currently relevant [10], where the negative syndromes of schizophrenia are considered to be the result of compensatory processes, pathological adaptation of the organism with the release of ancient defense mechanisms – schisis, autism, apathy-abulia, catatonia.

Phylogeny is adaptationogenesis, proceeding along the path of increasing systemic integration, differentiation, and specificity of responses, which is associated with the development of the central nervous system and the brain. Schizophrenia is not disorganization and breakdown of central functions, but its typical regressive form of adaptation.

The aim of the article is to use methods of logic, scientific generalization, extrapolation, systemic evolutionary analysis, and theoretical modeling, to reveal the adaptive nature of schizophrenia, that the procedural emotional-volitional defect is a universal form of biological adaptation.

Solving the problem of schizophrenia is of paramount importance due to its widespread prevalence, social and suicidal danger, and frequent loss of working capacity in patients.

which operate on the principle of feedback [12]. Emotions are a form of effective consciousness. The evolution of emotions follows the path of differentiation and socialization. Reflecting the body's current needs for substances, energy, and information necessary to maintain homeostasis, they carry the energetic charge of self-regulation and goal setting. Evolutionarily and genetically, emotions are paired with effectors processes in a “stimulus-response” manner and together form a single complex of general reactivity. The reactivity of the organism is associated with the energy modules of its vital activity. The energy characteristic of reactivity is temperament. Emotions are the center of motivation, goal setting, adaptive reactivity, systemic integration, and homeostatic regulation [6, 13]. Through the action acceptor, they regulate the movement of energy flows (metabolic, hormonal, and vegetative) in the body, generate the creation of functional systems, homeostat responsible for the realization of reflected needs, homeostasis, and survival. In phylogeny, reflecting basic needs, emotions generate the development of the soma as a superhomeostat, the central nervous system, the brain, higher forms of consciousness, and intelligence.

With the development of intelligence, the behavior of the organism as a whole system becomes increasingly mediated by dominant needs and becomes more complex.

Emotional centers, being a system-forming reactive structure, are also the center of self-awareness. The ego is a cluster of basic needs and related drives [6, 13].

The central nervous system (CNS) and brain have various energy modes and levels of operation, rigid and flexible determinants of regulation, which increase its functional plasticity and constitute biological adaptation.

The energy mode of operation is a variable that reflects the adaptive ability of the CNS and brain to temporarily change the energy range of their functioning. A change in energy mode is observed with changes in motivation, biological rhythms, fluctuations in affect [14], and compensatory processes. A low energy mode of the body's vital activity is postulated as depression.

The energy level is a structural constant, an innate value of the energy armament of the central nervous system and the brain, which determines the degree of basic reactivity and the power of homeostatic systems. A steady decrease in the energy level of the functioning of the central nervous system, the brain, and the entire body as a whole system is observed in schizophrenia [6,10,13,15].

Schizophrenia is the ability of the central nervous system, the brain, and the entire body as a whole system to switch to a lower, energy-saving level of functioning in order to preserve its structural and functional organization in pathological conditions [6, 10, 13]. The adaptive meaning of schizophrenia lies in the formation, through a pathological shift, an acute psychotic disorder of a specific emotional-volitional defect (EVD), which is a form of biological adaptation and leads to the removal of nervous and mental tension and frustration in pathological conditions. The organism's return to its original energy level of vitality is impossible due to the increase in the entropy of the system. The disease is based on adaptive mechanisms of systemic regression, an increase in the threshold of basic reactivity, and entropy. The clinical forms of schizophrenia reflect the body's innate defense response programs [16]. Schizophrenia is a disease of adaptation.

The emotional-volitional defect in schizophrenia is a specific energy defect that reflects the negative static nature of the disease. Positive syndromes of schizophrenia are nonspecific, reflecting the dynamics of the en-

ogenous process, the general patterns of functioning of the central nervous system, the brain, and the entire organism as a whole in conditions of pathology [6, 9, 10].

From the perspective of synergetic, the body is an open, unbalanced, self-organizing biological system that, in the course of its development, strives for systemic equilibrium and stability at the point of the main attractor through the dissipation of internal energy and an increase in entropy. The movement towards the point of equilibrium passes through systemic crises, catastrophes, transition points of bifurcation, intermediate attractors, leading the organism to entropic degradation and death at the point of the main attractor. The source of an organism's development is its internal conflict with the ecosystem.

Types of schizophrenia progression:

The types of progression reflect the nature of movement, dynamics, and progression of the endogenous process. The severity of the process does not always indicate its severity more often the opposite is true. The criteria for the progression of schizophrenia are [6]:

- a. The severity of EVD
- b. The speed of EVD formation
- c. The resistance of the endogenous process to therapy (indirectly).

According to the second law of thermodynamics, the progression of schizophrenia can only change for the worse. A benign course of the process can become malignant, but not vice versa. Acute polymorphic psychotic episodes of schizophrenia are observed with high reactivity of the organism, while its sluggish, schizotypal forms are observed with low reactivity, which is observed in the course of schizophrenia against the background of schizoidia [13].

Classifying all schizotypal forms as low-progressive processes is a methodological error. Low reactivity of the central nervous system, lack of acuity, and undeveloped clinical picture cannot be criteria for the progression of schizophrenia. Schizotypal forms often result in profound emotional and volitional defects, social maladjustment, and disability. Conversely, polymorphism, a developed clinical picture, and the severity of the process do not always lead to disability.

The classification of episodic schizophrenia with stable EVD in ICD-10 contradicts the adaptive nature of schizophrenia.

According to the author's hypothesis, each episode of schizophrenia increases the severity of EVD. Most likely, in this case, we are talking about variants of pseudopsychopath decompensation, rather than a schizophrenic episode as a progressive process [6]. Emotional-volitional defect is the adaptive goal and quintessence of schizophrenia.

The identification of a periodic type of schizophrenia contradicts the internal essence and adaptive nature of schizophrenia.

In schizoaffective psychosis, there is a mixture of various nosological units and mechanisms of biological adaptation:

- a. Adaptive reduction in the body's energy metabolism during a depressive episode.
- b. Adaptive reduction in the body's energy level during schizophrenia.

In schizoaffective psychosis, the use of antidepressants can remove the body's affective defense and aggravate the course of the disease [13].

Outcomes of schizophrenia:

The outcome of a schizophrenic episode is a neuropsychiatric defect.

A neuropsychiatric defect is a persistent loss or dissociation (disintegration, splitting) of neuropsychiatric functions [17, 18]. Disintegration of neuropsychic functions is equivalent to their loss. A neuropsychic defect is irreversible but can be compensated for [17, 18].

The structure of the neuropsychiatric defect in schizophrenia:

1. Emotional-volitional defect (EVD) with the release of ancient defense mechanisms—schizophrenia, apathy, abulia, autism, catatonia.
2. Cognitive deficit syndrome [19]:
 - a. immaturity, infantilism, autism, uncritical thinking;
 - b. dissociative thinking disorders: slippage, reasoning, diversity, fragmentation, schizophasia [20, 21];
 - c. disintegrative attention and memory disorders [21];
 - d. anosognosia.

Emotional-volitional defect (EVD) is specific to schizophrenia; it is primary and reflects the nature of the disease. Its essence is an energy defect [6]. The increase in the depth of EVD is a criterion for the progression of the

endogenous process [6]. Cognitive deficit in schizophrenia is secondary in nature, projecting the energy defect of the emotional-volitional sphere onto the cognitive functions of the central nervous system and brain, with a weakening of their motivational component, goal setting, and phenomena of anosognosia.

It is advisable to distinguish the following clinical types of EVD:

1. Asthenic (dependent).
2. Anxious (avoidant).
3. Hypochondriacally.
4. Dissocial.
5. Schizotypal (fershroben).
6. Autistic (euphoric).
7. Dissociative (disintegrative).
8. Apathetic-abulic.

It should be borne in mind that EVD can occur at various stages of ontogenesis, pathology of various body systems, consequences of traumatic brain injury, alcohol dependence, toxic effects of neuroleptics on the body, which causes its clinical pathomorphosis.

The types of EVD reflect variants of negative statics of the patient's mental state, which are based on the severity of the energy defect and its energy scale [6].

The identification of productive types of EVD is a methodological error, since they postulate clinical types of remission and dynamics, rather than the negative statics of the patient's condition [6].

Degrees of severity of emotional-volitional defect:

There is no classification of degrees of severity of EVD in ICD-10, although this is necessary for medical-social and forensic psychiatric examinations. The most severe types are dissociative and apathetic-abulic EVD, which determine the final state of schizophrenia. They have an anatomical and physiological basis: atrophy of the anterior parts of the limbic system and frontal lobes of the brain [22].

The severity of EVD reflects the degree of progression of the process. Each attack of the disease increases the depth of EVD.

Once the process of EVD formation has begun, it is difficult to stop because the body, as a holistic biological system, has already passed the point of bifurcation [23, 24] in its development, with the formation of pathological homeostasis and an increase in entropy:

1. Mild EVD: signs of asthenia, hypobulia, decreased gracefulness, regression of energy potential, secondary micro catatonia, autism, weakened motivation, and goal-oriented thinking are observed. There is no criticism of the disease. Social maladjustment. Working capacity is limited. Corresponds to the third disability group.

2. Moderate EVD: symptoms of hypobulia, ambivalence, autism, dissociation of thinking, secondary catatonia are observed. No criticism of the disease. Social maladjustment. The patient is unable to work. Work in therapeutic workshops is recommended. Corresponds to the second disability group.

3. Severe EVD: apathy-abulia, schizophrenia, disintegration, destruction of nervous and mental activity, terminal stage of the process. Patient's require care. Corresponds to they first disability group.

In addition to clinical types of EVD, subclinical latent types are also observed, since the procedural type of adaptation is universal. This manifests itself in "psychologically understandable" changes in the character and personality of the patient against the backdrop of biological crises, involution, somatogenesis, psychogenesis, and alcoholism.

Dynamics of emotional-volitional defect:

1. Increase in EVD – reflects the progression of schizo-

phrenia.

2. Stability of EVD reflects the outcome of schizophrenia, the formation of pathological homeostasis at a deficient energy level. A conditional period of stabilization, or stable compensation of EVD, can be assumed to be 3–5 years.

The dynamics of stable EVD are the dynamics of pseudopsychopathy:

a. Compensation phase: EVD traits are smoothed out, behavior is orderly, the patient is involved in work processes, and sub adaptation of the patient in the family and society is observed.

b. decompensation phase: protrusion of EVD traits, neurosis-like complaints, mood swings, sub psychotic symptoms, alcoholism, social maladjustment, and degradation are observed.

The phase of pseudo-psychopath decompensation must be differentiated from exacerbation of schizophrenia: in pseudo-psychopath decompensation, there is no autochthony, qualitative deepening of the clinical picture, or increase in negative symptoms, unlike in the current process. Decompensation of pseudopsychopathy is more often associated with social stress, exogenous factors, and somatogenesis.

In the phases of pseudopsychopathy dynamics, antipsychotic treatment is inappropriate, as there is no movement of the pathological process. They patient needs symptomatic treatment, psychotherapy, and social assistance.

but are suppressed and appropriated by higher, younger regulations. When new, younger functions are damaged, they can enter the arena of life.

4. Clinical forms of schizophrenia reflect innate programs of adaptive reactions of the body to stressors.

5. Positive syndromes of schizophrenia are nonspecific and reflect general patterns of the body's reaction to harmfulness.

6. In schizoaffective psychosis, there is a mixture of nosological units depressive episode and schizophrenia a combination of various mechanisms of biological adaptation:

a. temporary transition of the body to a low energy-saving mode of functioning—during a depressive episode.

Summary

1. In schizophrenia, there is a transition of the central nervous system, the brain, and the entire body as a whole system to a lower, stationary, energy-saving level of functioning. Clinically, this manifests itself in the form of a specific emotional-volitional defect. At the same time, ancient defense mechanisms are released – schisis, autism, apathy, abulia, catatonia.

2. The internal essence of EVD is an energy defect. The formation of EVD is an adaptation and, in pathological conditions, leads to the removal of frustration and nervous-psychological tension and the preservation of the internal organization of the organism.

3. Ancient regulations and defense mechanisms of the organism in the process of phylogenetic do not disappear,

b. a permanent transition of the body to a lower basic energy-saving level of vital activity with the formation of EVD – in schizophrenia.

7. Emotional-volitional defect is primary and reflects the inner essence and adaptive nature of schizophrenia. The increasing depth of EVD is a criterion for the progression of the process. Cognitive disorders in schizophrenia are secondary in nature, projecting the emotional-volitional defect onto the cognitive functions of the central nervous system and brain through weakened motivation and goal-oriented thinking, as well as phenomena of anosognosia.

8. Clinical types of EVD reflect the scale of energy defect. The most severe are the apathetic-abulic and dissociative types of EVD. These are the final stages of schizophrenia. The apathetic-abulic defect leads to a halt in cognitive processes, while the dissociative defect leads to schizophasia. 9. Anosognosia in schizophrenia is a hallmark of EVD, indicating the patient's loss of critical self-awareness against the background of an energy defect in the central nervous system, the brain, and the entire organism as a whole.

10. Schizophrenia is based on adaptive mechanisms of biological regression, the formation of pathological ho-

meostasis, and an increase in the threshold of basic reactivity and entropy. Schizophrenia is a disease of adaptation.

Conclusion

The transition of the central nervous system, the brain, and the entire organism as a holistic system to a lower, stationary, energy-saving level of functioning is a universal biological adaptation and reflects the internal nature and historical roots of schizophrenia. At the same time, an emotional-volitional defect is formed, which is an adaptive form of functioning of the organism in conditions of pathology; ancient defense mechanisms are released – schisis, autism, apathy, abulia, catatonia. The inner essence of the emotional-volitional defect is an energy defect.

Schizophrenia is based on adaptive mechanisms of biological regression, the formation of pathological homeostasis, an increase in the threshold of basic reactivity, and the entropy of the biological system. Schizophrenia is a disease of adaptation.

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